

Short communication

***Parapygmephorus delyorum* (Acari: Heterostigmata: Neopygmephoridae),
a species new to mite fauna of Iran**

H. Hajiqanbar^{1&*} and H. Rakhshani²

1. Department of Entomology, Faculty of Agriculture, Tarbiat Modares University, 14115-336, Tehran, Iran, 2. Department of Plant Protection, Faculty of Agriculture, Isfahan University of Technology, Isfahan, 84156, Iran.

*Corresponding author, E-mail: hajiqanbar@modares.ac.ir

چکیده

در پی جمع‌آوری شماری از زنبورهای خانواده‌ی Halictidae در استان اصفهان، تعدادی کنه به صورت مسافر (Phoretic) روی این زنبورها مشاهده و به نام *Parapygmephorus delyorum* Mahunka, 1980 شناسایی شد. این کنه برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شود.

The mites of the genus *Parapygmephorus* Cross, 1965 belong to the family Neopygmephoridae and are associated with halictid bees. They feed on fungi in the nests of their bee hosts and attach to the host via a large and strong single claw on their first tibiotarsus (Cross, 1965).

During a survey on bee family of Halictidae in Isfahan province, 3 specimens of phoretic heterostigmatic mites were found attaching to body hairs of an unidentified halictid bee. The specimens were collected by the second author on 17 August 2006 and are deposited in the Acarological Collection, Department of Entomology, Faculty of Agriculture, Tarbiat Modares University, Tehran, Iran.

The mites were later identified as *Parapygmephorus delyorum* Mahunka, 1980 which here is newly recorded from Iran. The genus *Parapygmephorus* is similar to the genus *Petalomium* Cross and differs from it by a large and strong claw on first tibiotarsus, solenidion ω on tarsus II rarely on apex of tibia II and a small pinnaculum (bearing tc'') on tibiotarsus I. Ecologically, the species of the genus *Parapygmephorus* are usually associated with halictid bees whereas the species of *Petalomium* are often in association with ants.

The genus *Parapygmephorus* includes six described species, of which *P. delyorum* was collected on a halictid bee in Korea (Mahunka, 1980) and its dorsal setae of hysterosoma, i.e. c_1 , d , f and h_1 are characteristically barbed in distal half.

References

- Cross, E. A.** (1965) The generic relationships of the family Pyemotidae (Acarina, Trombidiformes). *University of Kansas Scientific Bulletin* 45, 29-275.

Mahunka, S. (1980) *Parapygmephorus delyorum* sp. n., eine neue Art aus Korea (Acari: Tarsonemina). *Parasitologica Hungarica* 13, 95-98.

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